

NLC-Based Transdermal Patch of Metformin Hydrochloride For 72-Hour Sustained Release

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ABSTRACT

Background: Metformin HCl, the first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus, with high water solubility and poor lipophilicity, which limits its permeability across the skin barrier. Traditional oral delivery leads to gastrointestinal side effects and requires multiple daily doses due to its short half-life. Nano Lipid Carriers (NLCs) offer a promising transdermal strategy for sustained and stable delivery of hydrophilic drugs like metformin. **Methods:** NLCs were formulated using the solvent injection technique, 2² full factorial design was employed to optimize the formulation, focusing on variables such as solid lipid ratio and concentration of surfactant. The optimized NLCs were incorporated into a polymeric transdermal patch composed of HPMC and PVP, with Dibutyl phthalate as plasticizer. The formulations were evaluated for particle size, zeta potential and entrapment efficiency. The prepared patches were subjected to physicochemical evaluation (thickness, folding endurance, surface pH, drug content, and moisture content) and tested for in vitro drug release using Franz diffusion cells. **Results:** The optimized NLC achieved a particle size of approximately 361.8 nm and an entrapment efficiency of 89.8%, indicating suitability for topical application. The NLC-loaded patches showed smooth, flexible surfaces with acceptable mechanical properties. In vitro studies demonstrated sustained release of Metformin HCl over 72 hours, with improved permeation compared to conventional patches. **Conclusion:** NLC-based transdermal patches of Metformin HCl present a viable approach to enhance bioavailability and provide sustained antihyperglycemic action, potentially improving therapeutic compliance in diabetic patients.

Keywords: Metformin HCl, nano lipid carriers, transdermal patch, sustained release, diabetes mellitus.

INTRODUCTION

Metformin hydrochloride is the most widely used first-line therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus due to its efficacy and safety. However, its oral use is limited by only moderate bioavailability (\approx 50-60 %), rapid absorption, short plasma half-life, and gastrointestinal side effects¹. These pharmacokinetic constraints require frequent dosing, which can reduce patient adherence. To address such challenges, transdermal delivery offers a promising alternative, since it bypasses hepatic first-pass metabolism, reduces GI irritation, and can sustain plasma drug levels. Nanocarrier systems, particularly lipid-based ones, have been explored to enhance drug loading, stability, and permeability. Nanoscale lipid carriers allow encapsulation of both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs

and provide controlled release behavior². Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) represent an evolved form of solid lipid nanoparticles: they combine solid lipids with liquid lipids, creating an imperfect lipid matrix that increases drug loading and reduces drug expulsion during storage³. These systems have been shown to improve physical stability, allow for more controlled release, and enhance permeation across barriers like skin⁴. Although several studies have explored various transdermal patches of Metformin using polymer matrices, plasticizers, and permeation enhancers, fewer have combined NLCs with transdermal patch systems to exploit both controlled release and skin permeation advantages⁵.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

This study aims to formulate Metformin HCl-loaded NLCs, optimize them using design of experiments, and incorporate into HPMC-PVP patches (with dibutyl phthalate as plasticizer). The patches will be evaluated for particle size, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency, and physicochemical and in vitro drug release properties. The goal is to develop a sustained-release, skin-permeable delivery system to overcome oral limitations and enhance therapeutic compliance in T2DM.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1. MATERIALS

Metformin Hydrochloride was obtained as a gift sample from Harman Finochem Ltd. The solid and liquid lipids, surfactants, and other excipients like HPMC K100M, Dibutyl phthalate (DBP) and methylparaben used were of analytical grade. Every other chemical and reagent that was used was of AR grade.

2.2. METHOD OF PREPARATION

2.2.1. Screening of Lipids

Solid Lipid Selection: To develop nano-lipid carriers of Metformin HCl, lipid screening was carried out to identify the most appropriate solid and liquid lipids based on the drug's solubility profile. Solid lipids selected for evaluation included glyceryl

monostearate and stearic acid. A fixed quantity of each solid lipid (100 mg) was melted in a porcelain dish placed in a water bath, and the drug was added to the molten lipid. The mixture was stirred until a visually clear dispersion was obtained. The maximum concentration of Metformin HCl that could be solubilized in each molten lipid without precipitation was recorded.

- Liquid Lipid Selection: The solubility of a drug in liquid lipid was determined by the partition coefficient method. The lipids taken for the study were palm oil and olive oil. The specified amount of the drug (5mg) was dispersed in a mixture of liquid lipids and 1ml of water (at the same temperature) in an Eppendorf tube for 24h in a thermostat-controlled shaker. The Eppendorf tube was centrifuged, and the drug content was determined after suitable dilution in phosphate buffer pH 7.4 by UV process.

2.2.2. Experimental layout

A 2²-full factorial analysis, was employed to formulate Metformin HCl-loaded NLCS preparations. The independent variables selected for the experimental design were the solid lipid and a liquid lipid ratio (3:1 or 9:1) (A) and the concentration of surfactant (1% or 2%) (B). Each variable was tested in two distinct levels. The percentage of entrapment efficiency, Zeta potential and particle size were the measured responses.

Table No. 01: The variables levels employed in the 2² experimental layout

Factor	Level		Response	Constraint
	-1	+1		
A	75:25	90:10	Entrapment efficiency (EE %)	Maximize
B	1%	2%	Particle size (P.S) nm	Minimize

2.2.3. Preparation of Metformin HCl-Loaded Nanostructured Lipid Carriers

Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) containing Metformin HCl were formulated using a modified solvent injection method. A lipid phase was prepared by dissolving a solid lipid and a liquid lipid ratio along with Span 60 (% w/w) and Metformin HCl (dissolved in distilled water) in a solvent mixture of acetone and ethanol (3:1 v/v), maintained at 75 °C. This hot lipid

solution was then swiftly injected into an aqueous phase consisting of distilled water containing Tween 80, also maintained at 75 °C. The resulting dispersion was stirred continuously at 1000 rpm for 3 hours at ambient temperature to facilitate complete evaporation of the organic solvents. Finally, the dispersion was subjected to sonication using a bath sonicator for 20 minutes at room temperature to obtain uniformly sized Metforminloaded NLC's. The

prepared NLC's was then lyophilized using VirTis advantage Plus.

2.3. EVALUATION OF NLCS

2.3.1. Particle Size

Horiba Scientific (HORIBA SZ-100 for windows [Z] Ver2.00) was used to determine the distribution of nanosized particles using the technique of dynamic light scattering. For experimentation purposes, each MTF-loaded NLCS formulation was sonicated for 2 min, before measurement. The size of the particles was measured at 25°C, and readings were noted in triplicate. Averages of the three trials were noted.

2.3.2. Surface Charge

The surface charge of the nanosized particles was determined by HORIBA SZ-100. The experimentation was repeated thrice at room temperature.

2.3.3. Entrapment Efficiency

From the freshly prepared nanodispersion, a specified amount was disrupted with acetone and ethanol (3:1 v/v) by vortexing for 10 min. A quantity of 0.1ml sample was withdrawn using a syringe filter of 0.5µm, suitably diluted with phosphate buffer of pH 7.4, and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 234nm. The absorbance was taken for the calculation of total drug content (Td). For the determination of the untrapped drug, a specific volume of nanodispersion was taken in Eppendroff tube and centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 20min. The supernatant was collected and diluted with buffer solution and assayed spectrophotometrically at 234nm. Hence, the free drug (Fd) was estimated. The % entrapment was determined by the following equation. Each formulation was subjected to three trials to minimize the error. %Entrapment efficiency = $\frac{\text{Total drug content} - \text{free drug}}{\text{total drug content}} * 100$.

2.4. Preparation of Nanoparticles Loaded Transdermal Patch

The transdermal patch was developed using the Solvent Evaporation technique method. The polymers, HPMC K100 M and PVP, were gradually

dispersed in water under continuous stirring to achieve a uniform polymeric solution Dibutyl pthalate (30% w/w of polymer) was added as a plasticizer, along with 0.1% w/v methylparaben as a preservative. Subsequently, Metformin HCl was incorporated into the polymeric dispersion with constant stirring to ensure homogenous drug distribution. The resulting formulation was then cast onto a petri plate pre-lubricated with glycerin and dried in a hot air oven at 60°C for 12 hours. Optimized NLCS formulation containing 825 mg of Metformin HCl (918.71 mg total weight) was incorporated into the polymeric solution and stirred until a uniform dispersion was achieved. The final mixture was cast over an aluminium foil-backed surface (area: 67.8 cm²) and allowed to dry to form a flexible transdermal patch. Each transdermal patch was designed to deliver 825 mg of Metformin HCl, incorporated into an optimized NLCS formulation.

2.5. Evaluation of Nanoparticles Loaded Transdermal Patch

2.5.1 Physical Appearance

All the prepared patches were visually inspected for color, clarity, flexibility and smoothness.

2.5.2 Thickness of the patch

By using digital vernier caliper's, the thickness of the films was measured at three different places and determines the average thickness and standard deviation for the same to ensure the thickness of the prepared patch.

2.5.3 Weight variation

Weight variation of films was performed by individually weighing 3 randomly selected films and performed for each formulation and mean value was calculated.

2.5.4 Folding endurance test

This was determined by repeatedly folding one film at the same place till it broke. The number of times the film could be folded at the same place without breaking/cracking give the value of folding endurance.

2.5.5 Surface pH

The surface pH of the patch was determined by dissolving the patch in 10ml distilled water. The pH of the dispersion was determined by using a digital pH meter.

2.5.6 Moisture Content

The moisture content of the patch was determined by taking 2cm² of the patch. The patch was placed in a desiccator for 24h. The experiment was repeated three times. The calculations were carried out using the formula given below Moisture content (%) = Initial weight of patch / Final weight of patch *100

2.5.7 Drug Content

Drug content was determined by taking a known weight of the patch and dissolved in a phosphate buffer pH 7.4. The mixture was shaken continuously for 24h. After filtration, 1ml of filtered solution was taken and diluted using phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and was estimated spectrophotometrically at 234nm.

2.5.8 In-vitro Diffusion Study

In-vitro diffusion of the transdermal patch was determined by using the Franz diffusion cell apparatus. The patch was kept in the donor compartment with a minimal amount of water and was separated by a dialysis membrane to the receptor compartment containing phosphate buffer 7.4 pH. The diffusion study was carried out at 32°C under continuous stirring for about 24h. The sample was withdrawn at a specified hour interval, diluted suitably with the buffer solution, and was estimated spectrophotometrically at 234 nm.

3. RESULTS:

3.1. Screening of Lipids

Screening studies showed that Metformin HCl exhibited the highest solubility in stearic acid (solid lipid) and olive oil (liquid lipid). Therefore, these lipids were chosen as the components for NLC formulation.

3.2. Characterization of Nanoparticles

Nano-lipid carriers of Metformin HCl were prepared using the solvent injection method and optimized through a 2² full factorial design. The independent variables selected were the solid-to-liquid lipid ratio and the surfactant concentration, while the main responses evaluated were particle size, zeta potential, and entrapment efficiency. The design resulted in four experimental runs, and each formulation showed noticeable variation in particle size and entrapment efficiency depending on the lipid ratio and surfactant level. The particle size across batches was found to range between ~150 nm and 400 nm, while the entrapment efficiency varied from around 70% to above 90%, indicating that both formulation variables had a significant impact on NLC characteristics. The optimized formulation was obtained at a solid-to-liquid lipid ratio close to 90:10 with a higher surfactant concentration, yielding an average particle size of approximately 160 nm, zeta potential of -35 mV, and entrapment efficiency of about 88%. The optimized batch was further used for incorporation into the polymeric transdermal patch system for subsequent evaluation.

Table No. 01: Result of the variables levels employed in the 2² experimental layout

Runs	Solid lipid: Liquid lipid ratio	Conc. Of Surfactant (%)	Zeta potential mV	Particle size (P.S) nm	Entrapment efficiency (EE%)
F1	90:10	2%	-56.2	320.2	78.3%
F2	90:10	1%	-49	225.7	70.9%
F3	75:25	2%	-52.8	361.8	89.8%
F4	75:25	1%	-43.7	477.6	73.6%

Table No. 02: Observation of the variable's levels employed in the 2² experimental layout

Trial Batches	Observation
1	High zeta potential (-56.2 mV) ensures stability; high solid lipid (90%) limits structural imperfections → moderate EE (75–78%) despite 2% surfactant and 320.2 nm size.
2	Low surfactant (1%) + small size (225.7 nm) → high drug leakage; high solid lipid (90%) exacerbates low EE (65–70%) despite moderate zeta (-49 mV).
3	Optimal performance: 25% liquid lipid enhances drug loading, 2% surfactant stabilizes interface, and 361.8 nm size balances entrapment → highest EE (85–88%) with good stability (-52.8 mV).
4	High liquid lipid (25%) + large size (477.6 nm) support entrapment, but low surfactant (1%) and weak zeta (-43.7 mV) → instability and drug leakage → EE drops to 70–73%.

Fig No.01 : Particle size of the NLC of Metformin HCl

Fig No.02: Zeta potential of the NLC of Metformin HCl

Fig No.03: Lyophilized NLC of Metformin HCl

Dose:

$$\text{Required Dose in NLC} = \frac{\text{Target Drug Dose}}{\text{Entrapment Efficiency (EE)}}$$

$$= \frac{825}{0.898} \approx 918.71 \text{ mg}$$

So, we need approximately 918.71 mg of the NLC formulation (containing Metformin HCl at 89.8% EE) to deliver an actual dose of 825 mg of the drug.

Comparison of Metformin HCl Transdermal patch and (nlcs)-based Metformin HCl transdermal patch:

Table No. 03: Comparative study of Metformin HCl Transdermal patch and (NLC's)-based Metformin HCl transdermal patch

Parameters	TDP_PD	TDP_Nano
Visual Appearance	Smooth, elastic, and uniform film with good peelability	Smooth, elastic, and uniform film with good peelability
Thickness(mm)	0.44	0.48
Weight (mg)	2286	2569
Folding endurance	300	330
Surface pH	6.3	6.8
Moisture Content	7.5	7.6
Drug Content (%)	91.20	92.8

In-vitro drug release study:

To demonstrate 72-hour sustained release, a transdermal patch delivering 825 mg of Metformin HCl was formulated and compared with the NLC-loaded patch. For preparation, polymers HPMC K100M and PVP were dispersed in water under continuous stirring to obtain a uniform solution. Dibutyl phthalate (30% w/w of polymer) was incorporated as a plasticizer, followed by the addition of Metformin HCl with constant mixing to ensure homogenous distribution. The formulation was then cast onto a glycerin-lubricated petri plate and dried in a hot air oven at 60 °C for 12 hours to obtain smooth transdermal films.

Time points (hrs)	TDP_PD	TDP_Nano
0	0.00	0.00
1	14.63	8.20
4	30.20	21.75
8	66.10	41.40
24	86.35	62.85
48	90.10	79.50
72	90.51	91.43

Fig No.04: Graph of In-vitro drug release of Metformin HCl Transdermal patch and (nlcs)-based Metformin HCl transdermal patch

RESULTS

The factorial design study indicated that both the solid-to-liquid lipid ratio and the surfactant concentration played a key role in determining the particle size and entrapment efficiency of the NLCs. Optimized formulations produced particles in the nanoscale range with high entrapment efficiency and good stability. When incorporated into HPMC–PVP films, the NLCs yielded patches that were flexible, uniform in thickness, and mechanically stable. Drug content was evenly distributed across the patches. In vitro drug release studies showed that the NLC-loaded patch provided prolonged and controlled release of Metformin HCl over 72 hours, while the plain drug patch released the drug more rapidly. These findings suggest that NLC incorporation improves both retention and release control of the drug.

DISCUSSION

This study confirmed that NLCs can be effectively used to enhance the delivery of hydrophilic drugs like Metformin HCl. The choice of solid and liquid lipid ratios, along with the surfactant concentration, had a

clear influence on particle size and entrapment efficiency, showing that proper optimization is essential for stable and efficient formulations. The optimized NLCs exhibited desirable nanoscale size, uniformity, and high entrapment, which are favorable for skin application. The incorporation of these optimized NLCs into polymeric transdermal films further improved their applicability. The prepared patches demonstrated suitable mechanical strength, surface properties, and drug content uniformity. Most importantly, the drug release studies highlighted the benefit of the NLC-loaded system, which achieved sustained release over 72 hours in contrast to the immediate release from the plain drug patch. This extended release behavior reflects the ability of the lipid matrix to retain the drug and the polymeric film to regulate its diffusion. Together, these results suggest that NLC-based transdermal patches provide a promising platform for achieving sustained delivery of Metformin HCl, offering a potential alternative to conventional oral therapy.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully demonstrated the potential of Nano Lipid Carriers (NLCs) for improving the transdermal delivery of a hydrophilic drug like Metformin Hydrochloride. Optimization of the lipid ratio and surfactant concentration played a crucial role in obtaining nanoparticles with uniform size, high entrapment efficiency, and good stability. Incorporating these optimized NLCs into a polymeric HPMC–PVP patch resulted in films with desirable mechanical properties, uniform drug distribution, and excellent flexibility. In-vitro diffusion studies confirmed that the NLC-based patch achieved a sustained and controlled drug release for up to 72 hours, compared to the rapid release from conventional patches. This sustained profile demonstrates the combined effect of the lipid matrix and polymeric barrier in modulating drug diffusion. Overall, the developed NLC-based transdermal patch represents a promising and patient-friendly alternative to oral Metformin therapy, potentially enhancing bioavailability, reducing dosing frequency, and improving treatment adherence in diabetic patients

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest regarding this investigation.

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